

TRITECH Sefydliad
Institute

Evaluation Report

Bedside Entertainment and Communication
System (BECS),
Hywel Dda University Health Board

Report Produced: December 2024

Report prepared by:

Billy Woods, Clinical Scientist, Trittech Institute & Innovation.

With support from:

Joanne Connell, Clinical Research Nurse, Trittech Institute & Innovation.

Project Lead:

Richard Pearce, Senior Digital Project Manager, Hywel Dda UHB.

Evaluation Lead:

Professor Chris Hopkins, Head of TriTech Institute & Innovation.

Who We Are

In 2021 the Trittech Institute was launched. We are a team based in a bespoke facility within Hywel Dda University Health Board comprising of industry-leading engineers, scientists and clinicians.

Our Institute

Here at TriTech Institute, we support the development of healthcare solutions on a local, national, and global level offering designers and manufacturers a single point of access to the NHS through a collaborative and agile approach.

What We Offer

The team's advanced skills in clinical and research design are combined with technical engineering expertise to manage the whole innovative pathway from early unmet need, through to concept design, prototyping, clinical investigations, and real-world service evaluations.

Our Services

We provide specific services and solutions for clinical engineering, research and innovation and value-based healthcare and can also support with grant writing and submission.

Executive Summary

Background

Patient diagnosis, treatment, and rehabilitation take place in hospitals, where technological advancements have shortened the length of stay for certain procedures, such as surgeries (Fridh et al., 2015). However, for patients with complex health conditions requiring additional nursing support, the demand for hospital care remains high. Additionally, increased life expectancy has led to more patients with multiple co-existing diseases, further increasing the need for hospital services (Fridh et al., 2015).

Technologies such as smart bedside stations (SBS) offer services such as meal ordering, entertainment, internet access, and information about hospital services (Ryu et al., 2016). SBS can also allow patients to view scan results and learn more about their conditions and care plans. When properly implemented, SBS can enhance patient satisfaction and improve clinical workflows in hospitals (Ryu et al., 2016).

Bedside Entertainment and Communication System (BECS)

The Bedside Entertainment and Communication System (BECS) is a free service trialled at Prince Philip Hospital (PPH) by the digital teams at Hywel Dda University Health Board (HDUHB). This solution was introduced to address the challenges faced by patients during their hospital stay. BECS was implemented using a tablet or iPad at the bedside for patient use throughout their stay (HDUHB Digital, 2021).

Evaluation introduction

The TriTech Institute and Innovation team was commissioned to independently evaluate BECS. Prior to this, the digital team at HDUHB had gathered data for the evaluation, including user metrics and feedback from both patients and staff.

The primary aim of this evaluation was to identify any emerging benefits of BECS within the wards at PPH. The objectives included:

- Collecting, collating, and understanding available clinical data
- Performing statistical analysis and correlating it with BECS usage metrics
- Following up with clinical staff to gain further insights where applicable
- Generating a final report that incorporates all new data and existing results collected by the HDUHB digital team.

Methodology

To meet the evaluation objectives, a variety of data was collected and analysed. This included feedback from staff and patients, BECS usage data, and patient outcomes such as length of stay and incidents related to challenging behaviours and delirium. Reflexive thematic analysis was applied to the interviews conducted with staff and one service user (data was supplied by the by the HDUHB Digital team). The HDUHB Quality Improvement (QI) and Health Informatics (HI) teams provided data on length of stay (LOS), incidents of aggravation, and admissions related to delirium. Since no patient-identifiable information was available to trace individual service users and their BECS device usage, Mann-Whitney U tests were performed to compare data from before and during BECS use.

Findings

Reflexive thematic analysis of feedback from users and staff revealed several benefits of BECS for patients at Prince Philip Hospital (PPH). These benefits included an improved quality of stay, mental stimulation, a sense of routine, and reduced anxiety and stress. Feedback collected during the evaluation indicated that staff believe BECS can help occupy patients, preventing them from wandering off or accidentally injuring themselves. This was particularly noted as beneficial for patients with dementia. It was suggested that reductions in incidents or falls on the wards might be a more appropriate metric to measure than agitation or challenging behaviours.

The quantitative data collected for LOS, behavioural incidents, and delirium were inconclusive. In the absence of patient-identifiable information (PII) to link individual patients using BECS with factors such as LOS, it was impossible to determine BECS's impact on these areas. Additionally, user data for BECS, such as the average time spent on the device by each user, was not collected throughout the evaluation period, further limiting the ability to quantify benefits related to LOS, behavioural incidents, and delirium.

Conclusion

The qualitative data from user surveys and interviews indicates that BECS was well received by both service users and staff. Key benefits identified include reduced risks for service users who may become confused or wander off when unattended, and more efficient use of staff time, as occupied service users allowed staff to attend to others more effectively. Future evaluations should focus on quantifying these benefits to demonstrate the value of BECS.

To conclusively show the benefits of BECS, more quantitative data is needed. Collecting user data, including time spent on each feature and linking it to clinical outcomes using PII, will be crucial for future evaluations. Currently, HDUHB collects user data manually on the wards, as automatic data collection through the devices is not possible. Implementing login features or a method to track individual users or their PII (such as NHS numbers) would enable a more robust evaluation.

Recommendation 1: Development of an in-house solution that tracks individual service users

To achieve a more thorough evaluation of clinical outcomes in the future, it is essential to trace individual service users and their interactions with this technology. Developing an in-house software solution that allows service users to log in or collect PII will help facilitate this process.

Recommendation 2: Follow up evaluation of new solution

If recommendation 1 is implemented, a second evaluation period with an updated list of outcome measures (such as staff time and reduction in incidents or falls on the ward) will help further demonstrate the benefits of BECS. Baseline data and follow-ups for service users involved in the evaluation would be necessary for metrics such as the use of digital technologies and feedback on the quality of stay. This follow-up evaluation could include additional metrics such as the 4AT for delirium, though its suitability would need to be discussed with clinicians first. Staff time and cost savings should also be considered in this follow-up evaluation.

Table of Contents

Executive Summary.....	4
Acknowledgements.....	7
Abbreviations.....	7
1. Background.....	8
1.1. Service user experience whilst hospitalised.....	8
1.2. Technologies to help service users at the bedside.....	8
1.3. Bedside Entertainment and Communication System (BECS).....	9
2. Evaluation introduction.....	10
Evaluation aim.....	10
Evaluation objectives.....	10
4. Methodology.....	10
4.1.1. Reflexive thematic analysis.....	11
4.1.2. BECS service user survey.....	11
5. Findings.....	14
5.1.1. Reflexive thematic analysis.....	14
5.1.2. BECS service user survey.....	15
6. Discussion.....	26
7. Conclusion.....	28
References.....	29
Appendix 1 – Reflexive thematic analysis themes and codes.....	31
Appendix 2 – BECS use time in minutes.....	34
Appendix 3 – Mynedd Mawr most used BECS feature by week.....	37
Appendix 4 – LOS data for Mynydd Mawr.....	39
Appendix 5 – LOS data for Ward 1.....	40
Appendix 6 – LOS data for Ward 3.....	41
Appendix 6 – LOS data for Ward 9.....	43
Appendix 7 – Hospital admissions related to delirium.....	46

Acknowledgements

Hywel Dda University Health Board (HDUHB)

We are deeply grateful to Richard Pearce, Tina Davies, and the Quality Improvement and Health Informatics teams at HDUHB for their invaluable contributions. Their support in providing data and insights has been instrumental in evaluating and understanding the software's application within the University Health Board.

Abbreviations

4AT	Rapid Delirium test (Alertness, AMT4, Attention, Acute change)
BECS	Bedside Entertainment and Communication System
HDUHB	Hywel Dda University Health Board
HI	Health Informatics
HIT	Healthcare information technologies
IG	Information governance
PPH	Prince Philip Hospital
PPI	Patient identifiable information
QI	Quality improvement
SBS	Smart bedside stations

1. Background

1.1. Service user experience whilst hospitalised

Diagnosis, treatment, and rehabilitation of patients occurs in hospitals, and technological advancements have led to decreased length of stay for certain aspects of care, such as surgery (Fridh et al., 2015). However, for service users who have complex health conditions and require additional nursing support, the demand for hospital care is not reducing. Increased life expectancy is also resulting in service users who have multiple co-existing diseases which also results in increased need for hospital services (Fridh et al., 2015).

Hospitalisation can worsen a patient's psychological well-being (Chiarchiaro et al., 2013) and hinder their ability to cope and adjust (Alzahrani, 2021). It is crucial for healthcare providers to understand the impact of hospitalisation on a patient's well-being and to implement more interventions during these periods (Alzahrani, 2021). Increased stress in the hospital is also associated with a higher risk of major adverse health events post-discharge (Ford et al., 2023).

Post-hospital syndrome refers to a period of potential decline in a patient's ability to care for themselves after leaving acute care (Snyder & Fletcher, 2019). While a patient's illness can partly explain this decline, their overall experience in the hospital is also correlated with health outcomes (Snyder & Fletcher, 2019). Factors such as the quality of food, sleep, and access to entertainment can significantly impact patient experience (Snyder & Fletcher, 2019).

1.2. Technologies to help service users at the bedside

Healthcare information technologies (HIT) have evolved to enhance the quality, safety, and efficiency of healthcare delivery (Cho et al., 2020). Initially developed from the perspectives of healthcare providers, HIT technologies are now increasingly focused on incorporating the perspectives of patients (Cho et al., 2020).

Educating patients with multiple chronic conditions can be challenging due to the extensive time and learning materials required (Schooley et al., 2020). Patients who receive education through a combination of in-person sessions with health professionals and bedside digital tools show improved awareness and report increased motivation to care for themselves compared to those who do not receive additional education via bedside technologies (Schooley et al., 2020).

Hospital food services are a vital component of healthcare, and when managed properly, they can reduce the risk of malnutrition and enhance the patient experience (MacKenzie-Shalders et al., 2020). The use of digital technologies in healthcare food services, including bedside solutions, shows potential benefits for both patients and healthcare providers. However, more research is needed to fully understand the impact of these innovations (MacKenzie-Shalders et al., 2020).

Technologies such as smart bedside stations (SBS) can be used to provide services such as meal ordering, entertainment, access to the internet and information regarding hospital services (Ryu et al., 2016). SBS technologies can provide a source of entertainment for service users and enable them to view scan results or read more about their conditions and care

plans. When implemented correctly SBS can increase service user satisfaction and improve clinical workflows in the hospital (Ryu et al., 2016).

1.3. Smart Bedside Systems solution in Hywel Dda UHB

1.3.1 Bedside Entertainment and Communication System (BECS)

The Bedside Entertainment and Communication System (BECS) is a free service trialled at Prince Philip Hospital (PPH) by the digital teams at Hywel Dda University Health Board (H DUHB). This solution was introduced to address the challenges faced by patients during their hospital stay. BECS was implemented using a tablet or iPad at the bedside for patient use throughout their stay (H DUHB Digital, 2021).

H DUHB Digital issued the following problem statement as part of their business case for BECS: “There is a need to supply a modern patient communication and entertainment system for patients whilst they are in a hospital setting. This project will also allow further developments transitioning the Health Board towards the concept of a connected patient.” (H DUHB Digital, 2021).

Four wards were included in the evaluation of BECS, each with distinct clinical needs: general rehabilitation (Mynydd Mawr), respiratory (Ward 1), care of the elderly (Ward 3), and stroke rehabilitation (Ward 9). On these wards, an iPad was either placed next to each patient's bed or stored in a central location for patient access. Figure 1 shows a screenshot of the BECS interface. The H DUHB digital team anticipated the following outcomes from BECS in their agile business case (H DUHB Digital, 2021):

- Increased % of patients indicating they received good – excellent patient care
- Reduced Length of Stay due to preventing loss of cognitive function through interactions and stimulation.
- Increased volume of patients accessing interaction with family/friends
- Reduction in the volume of complaints related to inpatient stays
- Reduction in agitation and challenging behaviour
- Reduced % incidences of delirium
- Increase in the volume of patients using digital devices and accessing the internet and other services.

BECS offered the following services

- Radio / Music
- News, newspapers, magazines
- Internet
- Games
- Social media Services
- Telephone Calls (currently being developed)
- Video Calls
- Weather forecast
- Religious resources
- Opinion survey
- Notes
- Translate
- Information
- General information about the hospital
- Information about the Ward
- Team of specialists
- Access to service user environment on hospital site

Figure 1 shows the BECS iPad interface and the available options to the service user.

1.3.2 Evaluation of BECS

In January 2024, the TriTech Institute and Innovation team was commissioned by the HDUHB Digital team to conduct an independent evaluation of BECS.

2. Evaluation introduction

The digital team at HDUHB had previously collected data for this evaluation, including user metrics and feedback from patients and staff. This data was shared with the TriTech Institute.

TriTech Institute and Innovation were tasked with evaluating all of the data and feedback provided by HDUHB Digital teams, as well as collecting and evaluating additional data related to the following clinical metrics:

1. Length of stay in relation to prevention of cognitive decline.
2. Agitation and challenging behaviour.
3. Incidences of delirium.

2.1 Evaluation aim

The primary aim of this evaluation was to identify any emerging benefits of BECS within the wards at PPH.

2.2 Evaluation objectives

The primary objectives of this evaluation were:

- Collecting, collating, and understanding available clinical data
- Performing statistical analysis and correlating it with BECS usage metrics
- Following up with clinical staff to gain further insights where applicable
- Generating a final report that incorporates all new data and existing results collected by the HDUHB digital team.

3. Methodology

To meet the evaluation objectives, a variety of data was collected and analysed. This included feedback from staff and patients, BECS usage data, and patient outcomes such as length of stay and incidents related to challenging behaviours and delirium. Reflexive thematic analysis was applied to the interviews conducted with staff and one service user (data was supplied by the by the HDUHB Digital team). The HDUHB Quality Improvement (QI) and Health Informatics (HI) teams provided data on length of stay (LOS), incidents of aggravation, and admissions related to delirium. Since no patient-identifiable information was available to trace individual service users and their BECS device usage, Mann-Whitney U tests were performed to compare data from before and during BECS use.

3.1. Staff and service user feedback

3.1.1. Reflexive thematic analysis

HDUHB digital facilitated interviews with staff and service users on the wards at PPH who were involved in the evaluation of BECS. These interviews were filmed and transcribed by HDUHB digital and reflexive thematic analysis was used on the available material, based on the work by (Braun & Clarke, 2006). The interviews were conducted with 6 staff members and 1 service user. The six phases for reflexive thematic analysis used on this data are outlined below (Braun & Clarke, 2006; Byrne, 2021).

- Phase 1: Familiarisation with the data
- Phase 2: Generating initial codes
- Phase 3: Generating themes
- Phase 4: Reviewing potential themes
- Phase 5: Defining and naming themes
- Phase 6: Producing the results

3.1.2. BECS service user survey

HDUHB Digital created a survey for patients to gather additional feedback about the BECS devices and the services offered. This survey aimed to understand patients' perceptions of the technology and its impact on their hospital stay. It also included questions about the usefulness of various BECS features and demographic information.

Questions asked as part of the survey included:

- Has using the BECS iPad encouraged you to use more digital technology?
- Has using the BECS iPad increased your confidence in digital technology?
- What would make you use the iPad/Tablet more often?
- Were there any reasons why the iPad/Tablet was not used?
- Do you need support using the BECS device?

- How supported did you feel when using the BECS device?
- How would you rate the BECS service?
- Did this service improve the quality of your stay
- Did using this device help you stay connected with family/friends?
- Did using this device help you feel less distressed or anxious?
- Did using this device help you feel less lonely or isolated?
- Did using this device help keep you entertained?
- Did using this device help you keep up to date with current affairs outside of the hospital?

The survey also included questions to gauge the perceived level of usefulness of the various features on offer by BECS.

3.2. BECS use data

HDUHB Digital provided usage data for BECS on the four wards at PPH. This included metrics such as total device usage (in minutes), average daily usage (in minutes), and indications of which features were most frequently used by patients.

HDUHB Digital collected BECS usage data through the provided tablets, which was linked to the device rather than individual patients. As a result, it was not possible to correlate individual patient outcomes with their BECS usage or the specific features they used most frequently. The available use data for the four wards and the total time BECS was available can be seen in table 1.

Ward	BECS implementation date	User data available from	User data available to
Mynydd Mawr	16/05/2022	22/08/2022	07/11/2022
1 (respiratory)	03/10/2022	11/01/2023	21/02/2023
3 (care of elderly)	15/08/2023	28/09/2023	19/10/2023
9 (rehab and stroke)	27/06/2023	14/08/2023	27/09/2023

Table 1 shows the start date of the four wards included in the BECS evaluation and the dates of available use data for the devices.

3.3. Length of stay

Since it was not possible to link BECS usage data to individual service users, length of stay (LOS) data was requested for all service users on each ward. This was undertaken to identify trends during periods when BECS was in use and for a comparable period before its implementation. The data, anonymised to exclude patient identifiable information (PII), was provided by HDUHB Health Informatics (HI). HI reported the length of stay in days per service user from the date of admission.

Since no PII was collected, a comparison of median LOS across all service users was performed for periods before and during BECS use. This analysis, conducted using a Mann-Whitney U

Test in R Studio (R version 4.4.1), aimed to determine if the technology had any overall impact. The time frames compared for LOS across the four wards can be seen in table 2.

Ward	Pre BECS dates	Pre number of months	BECS of	During dates	BECS	During number of months	BECS of
Mynydd Mawr	May-21 to April-22	12		May-22 to April-23		12	
1 (respiratory)	Oct-21 to Sept-22	12		Oct-22 to Sept-23		12	
3 (care of elderly)	March-23 to August-23	6		Sept-23 to Feb-24		6	
9 (rehab and stroke)	November-22 to June-23	8		July-23 to Feb-24		8	

Table 2 shows data collection periods for the four wards for LOS.

3.4. Agitation and challenging behaviours

Similar to LOS data, information on agitation and challenging behaviours was collected for all services across the wards, as it was not possible to link BECS use metrics to individuals. The Quality Improvement (QI) team at HDUHB was contacted for this data. Information on all Datix incidents for the four wards during the periods shown in Table 2 was requested from HDUHB QI. The provided data included the classification of incidents (such as behaviour involving violence and aggression), along with the category and sub-category of each incident.

The data was filtered by ward and the number of incidents per month was summed. Since no PII was available, a comparison of incident frequency before and during BECS use was conducted using a Mann-Whitney U Test in R Studio (R version 4.4.1). This analysis aimed to determine if the technology had any overall impact on behaviour in the wards.

3.5. Delirium incidents

Similar to LOS data, information on delirium was collected for all services, as it was not possible to link BECS use metrics to individuals. Clinical teams at PPH were consulted about the tools used to measure delirium in service users. A geriatric consultant at PPH reported that the 4AT rapid clinical test for delirium is commonly used for assessments (Arnold et al., 2024). However, it was noted that in HDUHB, the use of this test depends on clinician judgment regarding when it is administered and how it is recorded. Consequently, it was not possible to collect any 4AT results from the wards at PPH.

Requests to HDHUB HI and QI teams were made to collect any recorded information for incidences of delirium on the four wards for analysis. The request was made using the timelines stated in table 2.

4. Findings

4.1. Staff and service user feedback

4.1.1. Reflexive thematic analysis

The original transcripts of staff and service user feedback are not included in this report. However, interpretations of this feedback and the codes generated through reflexive thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006; Byrne, 2021) are available in Appendix 1. The following section discusses the four themes identified from the analysis. A visual representation of these themes is provided in Figure 2.

Improved clinical services

Staff involved in the evaluation of BECS observed that service users who were occupied were less likely to cause disruptions or accidentally hurt themselves when wandering off due to boredom or restlessness. Knowing that service users were settled and entertained allowed staff to focus on other duties. This was particularly beneficial for some service users with dementia, as watching films or listening to music helped to calm them.

Reduction in anxiety / stress

Mental stimulation from the entertainment options was a welcome distraction for service users. Being able to occupy themselves with their own choice of entertainment offered a calming effect on service users. The ability to call family members and loved ones using BECS was also particularly helpful, as this helped to alleviate anxiety and stress outside of visiting hours.

Positive user experience

Staff and service users reported that using BECS provided a sense of routine and independence during their stay on the wards. Service users appreciated being able to choose their own entertainment and listen through headphones without disturbing others. This independence and variety of entertainment options were said to enhance the quality of their stay. Additionally, watching films or programs on the tablet was found to be more comfortable than using wall-mounted televisions.

Technology benefits

Many staff members and the one service user consulted during the interviews commented on the ease of use of BECS. Training service users on BECS was also found to be straightforward. Once service users learned how to use BECS, they frequently requested to use the devices. Staff were pleasantly surprised that both older and younger service users

Figure 2 shows a visual representation of reflexive thematic final themes for the use of BECS on wards within PPH, from information gathered during interviews.

were interested in BECS and encouraged other staff to consider using this technology on their wards. All interviewees noted the wide range of entertainment options available.

Other feedback from the interviews

Additional feedback from the interviews, not included in the reflexive thematic analysis themes, highlighted a few points: service users had to use the provided headphones, and having more free options, such as pre-paid Netflix accounts, would be beneficial in the future. Staff also noted that the HDUHB digital team was very responsive to feedback about the service and provided valuable assistance during its implementation.

4.1.2. BECS service user survey

A total of 63 service users were able to complete the BECS user survey, which had an equal split between male and females (49% female and 51% male). The frequency of age ranges of respondents can be seen in figure 3.

Figure 3 shows the age ranges of the BECS user survey responders.

Two questions asked were “Has using BECS encouraged you to use more digital technology?” and “Has using BECS increased your confidence in digital technology?”, the results of these can be seen in figure 4. Figure 5 shows the results of the question “How do you use the BECS tablet?”.

Has using BECS encouraged you to use more digital technology?

Has using BECS increased your confidence in digital technology?

Figure 4 shows the responses to two questions asked on the survey about the use of digital technologies.

Figure 5 shows the survey responses about frequency of BECS tablet use.

Of the 3 (4.8%) of responders that indicated they rarely used the BECS tablets, 2 provided feedback on what would help them use the technology more. Making the technology easier to reach and additional support to become confident with its use. Of the 18 (28.5%) of responders who did not answer the question shown in figure 5, 8 provided additional information as to why they did not use it at all. This feedback included already having their own tablet for entertainment, not knowing the technology was available, or not needing/wanting to use it.

Service users were asked to rate the BECS service from 1 to 5, with 5 being the highest rating. The responses to this question can be seen in figure 6.

Figure 6 shows survey responder ratings for the BECS service.

The BECS user feedback survey contained six statements in relation to the perceived benefits for service users, with Likert scale responses. These statements were:

- BECS helped improve your quality of stay
- BECS helped with staying in contact with family
- BECS helped with feelings of anxiety and stress
- BECS reduced feelings of isolation or loneliness
- BECS helped you feel entertained
- BECS helped you keep up to date with affairs outside of the hospital

The responses to these six statements were positive. Specifically, 80% of service users rated a 4 or higher for improved quality of stay, 71% rated a 4 or higher for BECS helping with feelings of anxiety and stress, and 71% rated a 4 or higher for BECS reducing feelings of isolation or loneliness. The Likert scale responses to these statements are shown in Figure 7.

The BECS user feedback survey also allowed respondents to suggest additional features and improvements for the service. Feedback included requests for more free services like Netflix, BBC/ITV channels, more sports options, and the ability to make phone calls in addition to video calls. Service users also expressed interest in having more games and activities. One respondent mentioned that features for visually impaired users would be beneficial. Overall, the additional comments were positive and appreciative of the service provided.

BECS helped improve your quality of stay

BECS helped with staying in contact with family

BECS helped with feelings of anxiety and stress

BECS reduced feelings of isolation or loneliness

BECS helped you feel entertained

BECS helped you keep up to date with affairs outside of the hospital

Strongly agree
 Agree
 Neither agree or disagree
 Disagree
 Strongly disagree
 Unanswered

Figure 7 shows Likert scale survey responses to benefits of using BECS on the wards for services users.

4.2. BECS use data

The available data on BECS usage in minutes across all four wards is detailed in Appendix 2. This includes average daily use (averaged over each project month) and total daily use (summed for each project month). HDUHB Digital could only record a portion of this data as it had to be manually downloaded on site, resulting in incomplete data.

Additionally, the BECS user data collected by HDUHB Digital included the most used features for each device, recorded weekly. YouTube was identified as the most used feature of BECS across all the data collected in Mynydd Mawr (see Appendix 3).

4.3. Length of stay

LOS data for Mynydd Mawr covered a pre-BECS period (May-21 to April-22, 12 months) and a period of time during BECS use (May-22 to April-23, 12 months). The LOS data for Mynydd Mawr can be found in Appendix 4. Figure 9 shows box plots for the pre-BECS and during BECS data for LOS on Mynydd Mawr.

The pre-BECS and during BECS data for Mynydd Mawr was compared using Mann-Whitney U and the results were: Test statistic ($W = 397.5$), significance value ($p = 0.1017$) indicating the two groups of data were not significantly different.

LOS data for ward 1 (respiratory) covered a pre-BECS period (Oct-21 to Sept-22, 12 months) and a period of time during BECS use (Oct-22 to Sept-23, 12 months). This LOS data can be found in Appendix 5. Figure 10 shows box plots for the pre-BECS and during BECS data for LOS on ward 1.

Figure 9 shows box plots for LOS data for pre-BECS and during BECS on Mynydd Mawr.

Figure 10 shows box plots for LOS data for pre-BECS and during BECS on Ward 1.

LOS data for ward 3 (care of the elderly) covered a pre-BECS period (March-23 to August-23, 6 months) and a period of time during BECS use (Sept-23 to Feb-24, 6 months). The LOS data for ward 3 can be found in Appendix 6. Figure 11 shows box plots for the pre-BECS and during BECS data for LOS on ward 3.

Figure 11 shows box plots for LOS data for pre-BECS and during BECS on Ward 3.

LOS data for ward 9 (stroke rehabilitation) covered a pre-BECS period (November-22 to June-23, 8 months) and a period of time during BECS use (July-23 to Feb-24, 8 months). The LOS

data for ward 9 can be found in Appendix 7. Figure 12 shows box plots for the pre-BECS and during BECS data for LOS on ward 3.

Figure 12 shows box plots for LOS data for pre-BECS and during BECS on Ward 9.

Table 3 shows the Mann-Whitney U test results for the four wards when comparing LOS data from pre-BECS and during BECS use. This includes the test statistic (W) and significance value (p) and it can be seen that there are no significant changes seen for any of the four wards ($p > 0.05$).

Ward	Test statistic (W)	Significance value (p)
Mynydd Mawr	397.5	0.1017
1 (respiratory)	1350.5	0.1263
3 (care of the elderly)	197.5	0.6358
9 (stroke rehabilitation)	1864.5	0.5521

Table 3 shows Mann-Whitney U results for comparisons of LOS for Pre-BECS and during BECS use across wards in PPH.

Trend analysis or correlation calculations were considered for the LOS data, using changes in average daily BECS usage data. However, as discussed in section 5.2, the available data only covered certain time periods. This is visually represented against all available LOS data in Figure 13. More usage data would be needed for a comprehensive correlation or trend analysis when comparing usage data to LOS over time.

Figure 13 shows summary data for LOS and average user time (average across month) for all four wards included in the BECS trial.

4.4. Agitation and challenging behaviours

Mynydd Mawr reported a small number of Datix incidents for challenging behaviors between May 2021 and April 2023, with only 8 incidents recorded. Consequently, there was insufficient data to compare pre-BECS and during BECS periods for Mynydd Mawr.

In ward 1 (respiratory), there were a total of 17 incidents relating to aggravated behaviours in the pre-BECS period and 19 in the during BECS period. This is visualised by month in figure 14.

Figure 14 shows the frequency of aggravated behaviours recorded in Datix for Ward 1.

Ward 3, there were a total of 5 aggravated incidents pre-BECS and 18 during BECS. Ward 9 had 6 pre-BECS and 13 during BECS. This can be seen visually in figures 15 and 16 respectively.

Figure 14 shows the frequency of aggravated behaviours recorded in Datix for Ward 3.

Figure 14 shows the frequency of aggravated behaviours recorded in Datix for Ward 3.

Table 4 shows Mann-Whitney U test results for 3 wards (not enough data for Mynydd Mawr) when comparing frequency of aggravation or challenging behaviour data from pre-BECS and during BECS use. This includes the test statistic (W) and significance value (p). It can be seen that there are no significant changes seen for wards 1, 3 or 9 (each $p > 0.05$).

Ward	Test statistic (W)	Significance value (p)
1 (respiratory)	64	0.6539
3 (care of the elderly)	10.5	0.2296
9 (stroke rehabilitation)	29	0.7766

Table 4 shows Mann-Whitney U results for comparisons of frequency of aggravation for Pre-BECS and during BECS use across wards in PPH.

4.5. Delirium incidents

The HDUHB QI team reported that incidents involving delirium are not routinely recorded on Datix unless there is potential harm to service users or staff. Therefore, they were unable to acquire any relevant data.

However, HDUHB HI was able to collate all service user hospital admissions to the four wards at PPH for the requested time periods. This included 17 admissions where delirium was one of the top three admission codes, as shown in Appendix 7. There was insufficient admission data to conduct a pre-BECS versus during BECS analysis for any of the four wards. Additionally, without PII, it was not possible to link these admissions to individual service users and their use of BECS.

5. Discussion

The discussion of the findings shown in section 5 are in the context of the anticipated outcomes from the original business case (HDUHB Digital, 2021).

Increased % of patients indicating they received good – excellent patient care

The user feedback survey distributed by HDUHB Digital included a question about whether BECS improved the quality of stay on the wards. Of the respondents, 51 (80.1%) agreed or strongly agreed, indicating that these service users felt BECS enhanced their stay. However, without a baseline score or another metric for comparison, it is not possible to determine a percentage increase in this metric.

Reduced Length of Stay due to preventing loss of cognitive function through interactions and stimulation

Reflexive thematic analysis of interview feedback from staff and one service user indicated that BECS provided mental stimulation and routine for those who used it. Additionally, 45 (71.4%) of survey responses were positive regarding BECS helping with feelings of anxiety and stress, and the same number (71.4%) indicated that BECS helped reduce feelings of isolation or loneliness.

No data related to cognitive function was collected, so this aspect could not be evaluated. Without PII to link individual service users' LOS with their personal BECS device use, it was not possible to investigate reductions.

LOS data was collected for the four wards, including all service users from periods before and during BECS use. This data was analysed for pre- and during-use periods for each ward, with no significant differences detected ($p > 0.05$). However, even if a difference had been found, other factors could have influenced the change. Correlation or trend analysis for LOS and average/total device use was also not possible due to insufficient user data covering the project period.

Increased volume of patients accessing interaction with family/friends

33 (52.4%) of survey responses indicated that BECS enabled service users to stay in contact with family and friends. Thematic analysis of interview feedback revealed that the video call feature was calming for service users, helped establish a sense of routine, and could reduce anxiety outside of visiting hours. However, without a baseline for comparison, it is not possible to calculate any change in the volume of patients accessing interactions with family and friends.

Reduction in the volume of complaints related to inpatient stays

No data on complaints was available for the four wards. If this data had been collected, it would have been compared across pre- and during-BECS periods, similar to other metrics. However, without more information about individual service users, it would be challenging to determine if any changes in the volume of complaints were due to BECS or other factors in the care of service users.

Reduction in agitation and challenging behaviour

The HDUHB QI team provided data from the Datix system related to behavioural incidents. Most of these incidents were violent in nature and were not discussed in detail for this evaluation. It would be challenging to demonstrate how BECS could prevent such incidents, even if it could keep service users occupied.

A pre- and during-BECS use comparison was conducted for the three wards with available data, but no significant differences were detected (all $p > 0.05$). Even if differences had been found, many other factors could have influenced the results. Therefore, this might not be a suitable metric for measuring the success of any future BECS system.

Reflexive thematic analysis of interview feedback indicated that staff believe BECS can help occupy service users, preventing them from wandering off or accidentally hurting themselves. This was particularly suggested to benefit service users with dementia. Reductions in accidents or falls on the wards may be a more appropriate metric to measure than agitation or challenging behaviours.

Reduced % incidences of delirium

Clinical feedback suggested that the 4AT rapid diagnosis tool could be useful for measuring or detecting delirium, though it may not be commonly used by all clinicians. Introducing this tool for service users engaging with BECS could help track changes over time, but this would need further exploration with clinical teams.

The HDUHB QI teams do not receive Datix reports specifically for incidents of delirium unless they involve potential harm or danger to service users or staff. While HDUHB HI provided admissions data related to delirium, the dataset was small and did not offer new insights into the relationship between BECS use and delirium.

Increase in the volume of patients using digital devices and accessing the internet and other services

The BECS user survey included a question about whether the technology encouraged more use of digital technologies. However, 43 (68.2%) respondents did not answer this question, and only 11 (17.4%) responded 'yes'. Similarly, when asked if BECS increased their confidence in digital technologies, 42 (66.6%) did not answer, and only 13 (20.6%) responded 'yes'. Despite this, 34 (53.9%) of respondents used BECS every day.

Without a baseline measure, it is not possible to determine any changes in the volume of patients using digital devices and accessing the internet. Nonetheless, 34 (53.9%) of survey respondents rated the BECS service 5 out of 5, and 16 (25.4%) rated it 4 out of 5, indicating generally positive feedback from service users. Additional feedback suggested that better access to internet services, more film and sport options, and access to free streaming services would further increase the use of BECS.

6. Conclusion

The qualitative data from user surveys and interviews indicates that BECS was well received by both service users and staff. Key benefits identified include reduced risks for service users who may become confused or wander off when unattended, and more efficient use of staff time, as occupied service users allowed staff to attend to others more effectively. Future evaluations should focus on quantifying these benefits to demonstrate the value of BECS.

To conclusively show the benefits of BECS, more quantitative data is needed. Collecting user data, including time spent on each feature and linking it to clinical outcomes using PII, will be crucial for future evaluations. Currently, HDUHB collects user data manually on the wards, as automatic data collection through the devices is not possible. Implementing login features or a method to track individual users or their PII (such as NHS numbers) would enable a more robust evaluation.

References

Arnold, E., Finucane, A. M., Taylor, S., Spiller, J. A., O'Rourke, S., Spenceley, J., Carduff, E., Tiegas, Z. & MacLulich, A. M. J. (2024) The 4AT, a rapid delirium detection tool for use in hospice inpatient units: Findings from a validation study; *Palliat Med.* 2024 May; 38(5): 535–545.

Alzahrani, N. (2021) The effect of hospitalization on patients' emotional and psychological well-being among adult patients: An integrative review; College of Nursing, Taibah Univesity, Janadah Bin Umayyah Road, Tayba, Medina 42353, Saudi Arabia.

Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77–101. [10.1191/1478088706qp063oa](https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa).

Byrne, D. (2021) A worked example of Braun and Clarke's approach to reflexive thematic analysis; *Quality & Quantity* (2022) 56:1391–1412 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11135-021-01182-y>

Chiarchiaro, J., Olsen, M. K., Steinhauer, K. E., & Tulsy, J. A. (2013). Admission to the intensive care unit and well-being in patients with advanced chronic illness. *American Journal of Critical Care*, 22(3), 223–231.

Cho, J., Kim, S., Shin, S., Yoo, H., Park, G. G., Jeon, E., Lee, E., Lee, H-Y. & Lee, E. (2020) Hospitalized Patients Accessing Information on Prescribed Medications from the Bedside Terminal: A Cross-Sectional Study; *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 2020, 17(13), 4850; <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17134850>

Ford, D. M., Budworth, L., Lawton, R., Teale, E. A. & O'Conner, D. B. (2023) In-hospital stress and patient outcomes: A systematic review and meta-analysis; Published: March 9, 2023 <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0282789>

Fridh, I., Kenne Sarenmalm, E., Falk, K., Henoeh, I., Ohlen, J., Ozanne, A., & Jakobsson Ung, E. (2015) Extensive human suffering: A point prevalence survey of patients' most distressing concerns during inpatient care. *Scandinavian Journal of Caring Sciences*, 29(3), 444–453.

Hywel Dda University Health Board Digital (2021) Agile Digital Business Case; Bedside Entertainment and Communication System (BECS).

MacKenzie-Shalders, K., Maunder, K., So, D., Norris, R. & McCray, S. (2020) Impact of electronic bedside meal ordering systems on dietary intake, patient satisfaction, plate waste and costs: A systematic literature review; First published: 19 January 2020 <https://doi.org/10.1111/1747-0080.12600>

Ryu, B., Kim, S., Lee, K-H., Hwang, H. & Yoo, S. (2016) Inpatient satisfaction and usage patterns of personalized smart bedside station system for patient-centered service at a tertiary university hospital; *International Journal of Medical Informatics* 95 (2016) 35–42.

Schooley, B., Singh, A., Hikmet, N., Brookshire, R. & Patel, N. (2020) Integrated Digital Patient Education at the Bedside for Patients with Chronic Conditions: Observational Study; JMIR Mhealth Uhealth 2020;8(12):e22947 doi: 10.2196/22947.

Snyder, H. J. & Fletcher, K. E. (2019) The Hospital Experience Through the Patients' Eyes; Journal of Patient Experience; <https://doi.org/10.1177/2374373519843056>

Appendix 1 – Reflexive thematic analysis themes and codes

Feedback statement (F0)	Codes F1	Codes F2	Theme
“BECS gives a sense of routine to service users”	BECS provides a sense of routine to users	Sense of routine	Positive user experience
“There is a general lack of mental stimulation for the service users on the wards”	Service users need mental stimulation on the wards	Mental stimulation	Reduction in anxiety/stress
“Stimulation and entertainment is helpful for service users who have falls risk and who might wander off, because being occupied means they are less likely to have an accident when not being actively monitored by staff”	Mental stimulation can reduce likelihood of injury when service users are left unattended	Reduce risk of accidental injury	Improved clinical service
“The entertainment options for BECS can be selected by the service user, which means that others on the ward do not need to watch the same shows”	BECS enables each service user to choose their own entertainment, with no disruption to other service users	Choice of entertainment & Reduced disruption	Benefits of the technology / Improved clinical service
“BECS is having a calming effect on service users”	The features available on BECS can have a calming effect on service users	Calming effect	Reduction in anxiety/stress
“The mental stimulation provided by BECS can help with feelings of loneliness and anxiety”	BECS provides mental stimulation which can help with feelings of loneliness and anxiety	Mental stimulation	Reduction in anxiety/stress
“BECS is helpful for staff if service users have something to do whilst they are helping other service users”	Service users being entertained or occupied by BECS free up staff time	Frees up staff time	Improved clinical service

“The range of entertainment options available through BECS means that a service user can find something that will keep them calm”	BECS enables service users to pick entertainment options most suitable to their tastes and mood	Choice of entertainment	Benefits of the technology
“BECS is helping with service user independence, because they can entertain themselves”	BECS is helping service user be more independent during their time on the ward	Independence	Positive user experience
“BECS is enabling contact opportunities for service users and their families outside of visiting hours”	BECS can keep service users in contact with families outside of visiting hours	Contact with families	Reduction in anxiety/stress
“The entertainment options available through BECS is helping to keeping challenging service users (such as those with Dementia) occupied. This can reduce the risk of service users hurting themselves accidentally and can keep them calm which can take some pressure off staff”	Entertainment with BECS can occupy service users with dementia and reduce their risk of accidental injury when unattended by staff	Reduce risk of accidental injury	Improved clinical service
“Occupied service users less likely to harm themselves accidentally when not bored”	Occupied service users less likely to harm themselves accidentally when not bored	Reduce risk of accidental injury	Improved clinical service
“BECS is easy to use for service users and staff are able to explain it easily to services users of all ages”	BECS is easy to use for service users and staff	Ease of use	Benefits of the technology
“Staff have been surprised at the number of elderly service users who wanted to use BECS”	BECS easy to use for older service users	Ease of use	Benefits of the technology
“Service users stay is increased in quality whilst using BECS”	Service users that are entertained have an increase in quality of stay	Increased quality of stay	Positive user experience
“Service users begin asking to use the BECS once familiar with its use and once they know it is there to use”	Service users want to continue using BECS after they become familiar	Continued use	Benefits of the technology

“BECS is a helpful distraction to younger service users who have never been in hospital before”	BECS can calm younger service users who have not spent time in hospital before	Calming effect	Reduction in anxiety/stress
“Staff surprised that young and old service users want to use the devices”	Service users young and old want to use BECS	All ages enjoy	Benefits of the technology
“BECS is helpful when work is busy on the acute wards. The staff can’t spend as much time with the service users as they would like, so BECS can give them something to do when staff are busy”	BECS can support staff productivity by entertaining service users, meaning less demand on their time	Frees up staff time	Reduction in anxiety/stress
“Staff are encouraging other wards to use BECS with service users. There is positive feedback after initial uncertainty with using the technology on the wards”	Staff feedback for BECS is positive and they encourage others to use it	Staff recommend it's use	Benefits of the technology
“BECS is settling and relaxing for service users with dementia”	BECS can help settle service users with dementia	Helpful with dementia	Improved clinical service
“Service users find watching TV easier on BECS than they do wall mounted TVs. This is because viewing angles are more comfortable”	Physically easier to watch TV through BECS than a wall mounted TV	Improved comfort	Positive user experience
“Hearing aids can cause some service users to not use the provided headphones”	There are physical restrictions to headphone use with hearing aid users	N/A - feedback to be covered separately	
“Some staff perceptions were initially unsure, but they have been surprised by how helpful BECS has been”	Staff initially unsure of BECS, but opinions improved after seeing it in use	Staff recommend it's use	Benefits of the technology
“BECS has also helped with service users who have cognitive impairments such as dementia, it keeps them calm and entertained”	BECS can help settle service users with dementia	Helpful with dementia	Improved clinical service
“HDUHB digital have been able to respond and action feedback for the service offered”	HDUHB have been able to improve the BECS service with feedback from staff	N/A - feedback to be covered separately	

“The range of features available on BECS is diverse”	BECS offers a wide range of entertainment features	Choice of entertainment	Positive user experience
“Service users needed their own login details for paid services such as Netflix, so options that are free at point of care would be beneficial”	Enabling more cost-free options to service users will improve the experience further	N/A - feedback to be covered separately	
“Being able to call family members using BECS is really comforting to service users, it can settle them during emotional periods”	The ability to call family members using BECS whilst on the wards is calming during emotional periods	Contact with families	Reduction in anxiety/stress
“Service users feel more comfortable watching their own programs on BECS knowing they are not disturbing other people on the wards”	Service users like that they won’t disrupt others when choosing TV shows to watch	Reduced disruption	Improved clinical service

Appendix 2 – BECS use time in minutes

ProjectMonth	MMTotalUse	MMAveUse	W1TotalUse	W1AveUse	W3TotalUse	W3AveUse	W9TotalUse	W9AveUse	All users
May-21									
Jun-21									
Jul-21									
Aug-21									
Sep-21									
Oct-21									
Nov-21									
Dec-21									
Jan-22									
Feb-22									
Mar-22									
Apr-22									

May-22									
Jun-22									
Jul-22									
Aug-22	712	120							51
Sep-22	2942	121							
Oct-22	5253	89							
Nov-22	1268	77							
Dec-22		15							
Jan-23			1571	26					978
Feb-23			25686	642					504
Mar-23			1140	57					880
Apr-23									1282
May-23									
Jun-23									
Jul-23									
Aug-23							1399	59	
Sep-23					0	0	2168	45	
Oct-23					0	0			
Nov-23									1204
Dec-23				99		16		107	
Jan-24									
Feb-24									

Figure 15 shows the available total use data for BECS across the wards that trialed it in PPH.

Appendix 3 – Mynedd Mawr most used BECS feature by week

Device Name	22/08/2022	29/08/2022	05/09/2022	12/09/2022	19/9/2022	26/09/2022	03/10/2022	10/10/2022	17/10/2022	24/10/2022	31/10/2022	07/11/2022
PPH-001	borrow box	YouTu be	YouTu be	YouTu be	YouTu be	YouTu be	YouTu be	fire fox	YouTu be	YouTu be	borro w box	BECS
PPH-002	BECS	BECS	BECS	YouTu be	borro w box	YouTu be	YouTu be	netflix	COVID POSTI VE	COVID	YouTu be	YouTu be
PPH-003	ONLY LOCK SCREEN AND SETTINGS USED.	BECS	setting s	YouTu be	YouTu be	YouTu be	YouTu be	fire fox	YouTu be	YouTu be	YouTu be	borro w box
PPH-004	BECS	YouTu be	YouTu be	YouTu be	YouTu be	YouTu be	BECS	fire fox	BECS	YouTu be	YouTu be	YouTu be
PPH-005	YouTube	YouTu be	YouTu be	YouTu be	YouTu be	YouTu be	BECS	fire fox	BECS	BECS	BECS	netflix
PPH-006	YouTube	YouTu be	YouTu be	YouTu be	YouTu be	YouTu be	YouTu be	fire fox	YouTu be	COVID	YouTu be	YouTu be
PPH-007	YouTube	BECS	YouTu be	YouTu be	YouTu be	YouTu be	YouTu be	fire fox	YouTu be	YouTu be	YouTu be	YouTu be
PPH-008	BECS	YouTu be	BECS	n/a	YouTu be	BECS	YouTu be	netflix	YouTu be	YouTu be	YouTu be	BECS
PPH-009	BECS	BECS	BECS	BECS	BECS	BECS	YouTu be	BECS	YouTu be	YouTu be	YouTu be	YouTu be
PPH-010	YouTube	N/A	YouTu be	YouTu be	YouTu be	YouTu be	YouTu be	fire fox	NOT IN USE	SETTIN GS	not in use	not
PPH-011	YouTube	YouTu be	BECS	BECS	BECS	setting s	BECS	NOT IN USE	NOT IN USE	not in use	not in use	not
PPH-012	YouTube	YouTu be	YouTu be	YouTu be	YouTu be	YouTu be	setting s	NOT IN USE	NOT IN USE	not in use	not in use	not

PPH-013	BECS	borro w box	borro w box	BECS	BECS	BECS	borro w box	Borro w box	Borro w box	borro w box	BECS	YouTu be
PPH-014	YouTube	BECS	BECS	BECS	BECS	YouTu be	YouTu be	YouTu be	Borro w box	YouTu be	YouTu be	BECS
PPH-015	YouTube	YouTu be	YouTu be	YouTu be	YouTu be	YouTu be	fire fox	fire fox	YouTu be	YouTu be	YouTu be	YouTu be
Most Used	YouTube	YouTu be	YouTu be	YouTu be	YouT ube	YouTu be	YouTu be	fire fox	YouTu be	YouTu be	YouTu be	YouTu be

Appendix 4 – LOS data for Mynydd Mawr

AdmissionDate	DischargeDate	LOS	AdmissionDate	DischargeDate	LOS
06/05/2021	21/06/2021	46	02/07/2022	22/11/2022	143
10/05/2021	17/05/2021	7	07/07/2022	08/07/2022	1
11/05/2021	04/06/2021	24	08/07/2022	12/11/2022	127
12/05/2021	11/06/2021	30	19/07/2022	04/08/2022	16
13/05/2021	15/06/2021	33	22/07/2022	28/10/2022	98
22/05/2021	11/06/2021	20	28/07/2022	06/09/2022	40
12/06/2021	16/06/2021	4	11/08/2022	23/09/2022	43
14/06/2021	23/06/2021	9	24/09/2022	14/03/2023	171
18/06/2021	28/08/2021	71	29/09/2022	01/11/2022	33
24/06/2021	09/07/2021	15	22/10/2022	06/01/2023	76
09/07/2021	27/07/2021	18	04/11/2022	29/12/2022	55
22/07/2021	14/02/2022	207	03/12/2022	31/03/2023	118
05/08/2021	08/11/2021	95	06/12/2022	20/12/2022	14
11/08/2021	03/11/2021	84	15/12/2022	30/01/2023	46
01/09/2021	03/11/2021	63	15/12/2022	18/01/2023	34
06/09/2021	01/11/2021	56	07/01/2023	25/01/2023	18
18/09/2021	08/10/2021	20	12/01/2023	24/01/2023	12
07/10/2021	05/11/2021	29	12/01/2023	03/05/2023	111
07/10/2021	05/11/2021	29	24/01/2023	16/05/2023	112
08/10/2021	13/10/2021	5	25/01/2023	22/02/2023	28
13/10/2021	29/01/2022	108	30/01/2023	09/07/2023	160
23/10/2021	23/12/2021	61	07/02/2023	15/02/2023	8
01/11/2021	06/11/2021	5	18/02/2023	17/04/2023	58
02/11/2021	13/11/2021	11	17/04/2023	24/04/2023	7
10/11/2021	24/11/2021	14	26/04/2023	26/06/2023	61
10/11/2021	11/11/2021	1	10/05/2023	24/08/2023	106
14/11/2021	24/11/2021	10	08/06/2023	10/08/2023	63
02/12/2021	21/06/2022	201	12/06/2023	08/07/2023	26
08/12/2021	21/02/2022	75	29/06/2023	22/08/2023	54
14/12/2021	25/05/2022	162	30/06/2023	12/07/2023	12
19/01/2022	25/02/2022	37	12/07/2023	20/09/2023	70
19/01/2022	19/01/2022	0	01/08/2023	02/11/2023	93
21/01/2022	04/04/2022	73	03/08/2023	11/10/2023	69
28/01/2022	23/02/2022	26	17/08/2023	05/09/2023	19
01/03/2022	31/03/2022	30	03/10/2023	12/01/2024	101
03/03/2022	16/11/2022	258	06/11/2023	06/02/2024	92
31/05/2022	18/07/2022	48	06/12/2023	20/12/2023	14
02/06/2022	22/09/2022	112	28/12/2023	28/02/2024	62
07/06/2022	19/07/2022	42	05/01/2024	25/01/2024	20
21/06/2022	02/03/2023	254	01/02/2024	03/04/2024	62

Appendix 5 – LOS data for Ward 1

AdmissionDate	DischargeDate	LOS	AdmissionDate	DischargeDate	LOS
01/05/2021	22/06/2021	52	16/09/2022	20/09/2022	4
16/05/2021	18/05/2021	2	16/09/2022	03/02/2023	140
22/05/2021	23/05/2021	1	07/10/2022	11/10/2022	4
03/06/2021	05/06/2021	2	11/10/2022	16/11/2022	36
13/06/2021	22/07/2021	39	12/10/2022	17/10/2022	5
13/06/2021	16/06/2021	3	05/11/2022	22/12/2022	47
25/06/2021	20/08/2021	56	18/11/2022	14/12/2022	26
29/06/2021	23/07/2021	24	18/11/2022	24/11/2022	6
08/07/2021	09/07/2021	1	28/11/2022	02/12/2022	4
14/07/2021	15/07/2021	1	17/12/2022	24/12/2022	7
14/07/2021	16/07/2021	2	23/12/2022	03/01/2023	11
17/07/2021	03/09/2021	48	23/12/2022	30/12/2022	7
18/07/2021	05/10/2021	79	30/12/2022	31/01/2023	32
19/07/2021	27/07/2021	8	04/01/2023	06/01/2023	2
22/07/2021	01/09/2021	41	06/01/2023	06/01/2023	0
31/07/2021	10/08/2021	10	06/01/2023	19/01/2023	13
05/08/2021	16/08/2021	11	06/01/2023	22/01/2023	16
06/08/2021	07/08/2021	1	07/01/2023	30/01/2023	23
24/08/2021	01/09/2021	8	13/01/2023	26/04/2023	103
26/08/2021	13/10/2021	48	18/01/2023	25/01/2023	7
02/09/2021	23/09/2021	21	18/01/2023	24/01/2023	6
02/09/2021	28/09/2021	26	19/01/2023	28/02/2023	40
13/09/2021	24/09/2021	11	20/01/2023	17/04/2023	87
14/09/2021	23/09/2021	9	15/02/2023	19/04/2023	63
05/10/2021	20/01/2022	107	16/02/2023	15/03/2023	27
08/10/2021	26/11/2021	49	17/02/2023	16/05/2023	88
12/10/2021	27/10/2021	15	04/03/2023	02/05/2023	59
12/10/2021	27/10/2021	15	24/03/2023	24/05/2023	61
14/10/2021	02/11/2021	19	27/04/2023	18/08/2023	113
23/10/2021	01/11/2021	9	04/05/2023	10/05/2023	6
28/10/2021	30/10/2021	2	06/05/2023	21/06/2023	46
12/11/2021	15/11/2021	3	23/05/2023	16/06/2023	24
13/11/2021	16/11/2021	3	01/06/2023	02/06/2023	1
16/11/2021	07/01/2022	52	10/06/2023	12/06/2023	2
25/11/2021	14/12/2021	19	17/06/2023	20/09/2023	95
07/12/2021	10/12/2021	3	20/06/2023	27/06/2023	7
10/12/2021	15/12/2021	5	20/06/2023	25/09/2023	97
16/12/2021	17/12/2021	1	27/06/2023	29/06/2023	2
21/12/2021	26/12/2021	5	13/07/2023	14/07/2023	1
27/12/2021	31/12/2021	4	15/07/2023	07/09/2023	54
01/01/2022	28/01/2022	27	15/07/2023	25/07/2023	10
12/01/2022	23/01/2022	11	16/07/2023	02/08/2023	17
17/01/2022	21/01/2022	4	19/07/2023	24/07/2023	5

01/02/2022	03/02/2022	2	27/07/2023	28/07/2023	1
04/02/2022	08/02/2022	4	29/07/2023	19/12/2023	143
14/02/2022	28/02/2022	14	03/08/2023	04/08/2023	1
18/02/2022	28/02/2022	10	04/08/2023	08/08/2023	4
01/03/2022	11/03/2022	10	08/08/2023	13/08/2023	5
07/03/2022	11/03/2022	4	11/08/2023	14/08/2023	3
25/03/2022	26/03/2022	1	15/08/2023	24/08/2023	9
13/04/2022	22/04/2022	9	15/08/2023	21/08/2023	6
14/04/2022	15/04/2022	1	16/08/2023	26/09/2023	41
25/04/2022	27/04/2022	2	21/08/2023	21/08/2023	0
26/04/2022	10/05/2022	14	21/08/2023	24/08/2023	3
27/04/2022	06/05/2022	9	22/08/2023	07/09/2023	16
05/05/2022	09/05/2022	4	22/08/2023	30/08/2023	8
11/05/2022	15/05/2022	4	24/08/2023	07/09/2023	14
12/05/2022	25/08/2022	105	16/09/2023	19/09/2023	3
17/05/2022	20/05/2022	3	19/09/2023	02/10/2023	13
20/05/2022	06/06/2022	17	20/09/2023	24/09/2023	4
20/05/2022	20/05/2022	0	21/09/2023	04/10/2023	13
15/06/2022	08/07/2022	23	26/09/2023	29/09/2023	3
17/06/2022	20/06/2022	3	18/10/2023	22/10/2023	4
17/06/2022	07/12/2022	173	23/10/2023	16/11/2023	24
29/06/2022	30/06/2022	1	02/11/2023	10/11/2023	8
04/07/2022	13/07/2022	9	02/11/2023	11/11/2023	9
25/07/2022	09/08/2022	15	13/11/2023	17/11/2023	4
26/07/2022	30/07/2022	4	20/11/2023	24/11/2023	4
27/07/2022	01/09/2022	36	28/11/2023	11/12/2023	13
02/08/2022	05/09/2022	34	11/01/2024	19/03/2024	68
16/08/2022	18/08/2022	2	26/01/2024	29/01/2024	3
17/08/2022	24/08/2022	7	30/01/2024	02/02/2024	3
24/08/2022	02/09/2022	9	08/02/2024	19/02/2024	11
08/09/2022	09/09/2022	1	19/02/2024	23/02/2024	4
08/09/2022	09/09/2022	1	28/02/2024	05/03/2024	6
15/09/2022	20/09/2022	5			

Appendix 6 – LOS data for Ward 3

AdmissionDate	DischargeDate	LOS	AdmissionDate	DischargeDate	LOS
10/06/2021	11/08/2021	62	15/11/2022	24/01/2023	70
11/06/2021	18/06/2021	7	28/11/2022	02/12/2022	4
11/06/2021	17/06/2021	6	13/12/2022	21/01/2023	39
18/06/2021	25/06/2021	7	23/12/2022	17/05/2023	145
30/06/2021	06/07/2021	6	30/12/2022	04/01/2023	5

05/07/2021	21/09/2021	78	04/01/2023	09/01/2023	5
21/07/2021	22/07/2021	1	05/01/2023	16/01/2023	11
22/07/2021	13/08/2021	22	06/01/2023	31/01/2023	25
04/08/2021	01/11/2021	89	16/01/2023	24/01/2023	8
13/08/2021	31/08/2021	18	18/01/2023	23/01/2023	5
02/09/2021	13/10/2021	41	23/01/2023	03/03/2023	39
04/09/2021	04/11/2021	61	31/01/2023	19/05/2023	108
06/09/2021	13/09/2021	7	01/02/2023	25/07/2023	174
01/10/2021	04/10/2021	3	23/02/2023	25/03/2023	30
19/10/2021	19/10/2021	0	02/03/2023	06/03/2023	4
20/10/2021	08/02/2022	111	22/03/2023	28/03/2023	6
28/10/2021	22/01/2022	86	22/03/2023	03/04/2023	12
09/11/2021	23/12/2021	44	25/03/2023	04/04/2023	10
23/11/2021	29/11/2021	6	06/04/2023	27/06/2023	82
24/11/2021	02/12/2021	8	07/04/2023	14/04/2023	7
01/12/2021	07/07/2022	218	18/04/2023	29/06/2023	72
05/12/2021	16/12/2021	11	20/04/2023	07/08/2023	109
17/12/2021	17/02/2022	62	04/05/2023	13/05/2023	9
21/12/2021	24/12/2021	3	15/05/2023	23/05/2023	8
22/12/2021	18/01/2022	27	22/05/2023	23/06/2023	32
08/01/2022	28/01/2022	20	25/05/2023	24/10/2023	152
13/01/2022	21/01/2022	8	01/06/2023	09/08/2023	69
19/01/2022	19/02/2022	31	08/06/2023	19/06/2023	11
19/01/2022	19/05/2022	120	20/06/2023	06/11/2023	139
31/01/2022	20/07/2022	170	24/06/2023	15/09/2023	83
09/02/2022	03/05/2022	83	27/06/2023	03/10/2023	98
14/02/2022	23/02/2022	9	28/06/2023	29/06/2023	1
17/02/2022	18/02/2022	1	29/06/2023	05/07/2023	6
22/02/2022	28/02/2022	6	10/07/2023	25/07/2023	15
07/03/2022	09/03/2022	2	14/07/2023	16/07/2023	2
07/03/2022	08/03/2022	1	17/07/2023	06/10/2023	81
28/03/2022	19/04/2022	22	27/07/2023	05/09/2023	40
29/03/2022	31/05/2022	63	28/07/2023	05/12/2023	130
31/03/2022	02/04/2022	2	28/07/2023	20/09/2023	54
07/04/2022	04/05/2022	27	10/08/2023	30/08/2023	20
17/04/2022	18/05/2022	31	10/08/2023	18/08/2023	8
03/05/2022	07/07/2022	65	14/08/2023	15/09/2023	32
05/05/2022	25/05/2022	20	14/08/2023	22/08/2023	8
07/05/2022	15/07/2022	69	24/08/2023	01/11/2023	69
16/05/2022	27/06/2022	42	02/09/2023	30/09/2023	28
17/05/2022	18/05/2022	1	05/09/2023	24/11/2023	80
31/05/2022	13/06/2022	13	06/09/2023	10/10/2023	34
31/05/2022	29/07/2022	59	10/09/2023	26/09/2023	16
06/06/2022	10/06/2022	4	10/10/2023	17/10/2023	7
13/06/2022	15/06/2022	2	13/12/2023	28/01/2024	46

28/07/2022	01/08/2022	4	24/12/2023	18/01/2024	25
06/08/2022	17/09/2022	42	15/01/2024	16/01/2024	1
09/08/2022	26/09/2022	48	19/01/2024	29/01/2024	10
22/09/2022	21/10/2022	29	22/01/2024	11/03/2024	49
11/10/2022	14/10/2022	3	23/02/2024	08/03/2024	14
14/11/2022	30/11/2022	16	29/02/2024	19/03/2024	19

Appendix 6 – LOS data for Ward 9

AdmissionDate	DischargeDate	LOS	AdmissionDate	DischargeDate	LOS
22/05/2021	01/08/2021	71	26/09/2022	28/09/2022	2
26/05/2021	27/05/2021	1	05/10/2022	12/10/2022	7
28/05/2021	02/06/2021	5	08/10/2022	09/12/2022	62
02/06/2021	08/06/2021	6	19/10/2022	26/10/2022	7
04/06/2021	10/06/2021	6	25/10/2022	18/10/2023	358
15/06/2021	24/06/2021	9	16/11/2022	18/11/2022	2
17/06/2021	19/07/2021	32	19/11/2022	23/12/2022	34
26/06/2021	28/06/2021	2	21/11/2022	05/12/2022	14
26/06/2021	09/07/2021	13	23/11/2022	17/03/2023	114
05/07/2021	18/07/2021	13	26/11/2022	30/12/2022	34
09/07/2021	15/07/2021	6	02/12/2022	08/12/2022	6
13/07/2021	26/10/2021	105	05/12/2022	28/02/2023	85
15/07/2021	26/07/2021	11	07/12/2022	16/12/2022	9
20/07/2021	21/07/2021	1	30/12/2022	06/01/2023	7
23/07/2021	15/09/2021	54	30/12/2022	01/01/2023	2
28/07/2021	05/11/2021	100	30/12/2022	13/01/2023	14
01/08/2021	04/08/2021	3	03/01/2023	05/01/2023	2
02/08/2021	09/08/2021	7	09/01/2023	25/01/2023	16
05/08/2021	07/08/2021	2	24/01/2023	20/10/2023	269
05/08/2021	05/08/2021	0	26/01/2023	12/05/2023	106
05/08/2021	13/09/2021	39	28/01/2023	19/04/2023	81
06/08/2021	07/08/2021	1	31/01/2023	10/02/2023	10
11/08/2021	18/08/2021	7	07/02/2023	13/02/2023	6
18/08/2021	03/11/2021	77	07/02/2023	16/02/2023	9
18/08/2021	20/08/2021	2	24/02/2023	24/02/2023	0
19/08/2021	19/08/2021	0	01/03/2023	03/03/2023	2
20/08/2021	14/09/2021	25	14/03/2023	20/03/2023	6
25/08/2021	17/09/2021	23	17/03/2023	03/04/2023	17
01/09/2021	02/09/2021	1	21/03/2023	11/04/2023	21
05/09/2021	06/09/2021	1	24/03/2023	27/03/2023	3
16/09/2021	18/09/2021	2	29/03/2023	02/04/2023	4
18/09/2021	22/09/2021	4	05/04/2023	19/04/2023	14
23/09/2021	24/09/2021	1	06/04/2023	25/07/2023	110
23/09/2021	14/12/2021	82	07/04/2023	26/07/2023	110
27/09/2021	28/09/2021	1	08/04/2023	16/04/2023	8

04/10/2021	20/12/2021	77	08/04/2023	14/09/2023	159
04/10/2021	15/10/2021	11	10/04/2023	11/04/2023	1
04/10/2021	06/10/2021	2	11/04/2023	12/04/2023	1
06/10/2021	18/10/2021	12	23/04/2023	02/06/2023	40
06/10/2021	08/10/2021	2	23/04/2023	23/04/2023	0
07/10/2021	08/10/2021	1	27/04/2023	02/05/2023	5
08/10/2021	28/10/2021	20	13/05/2023	15/05/2023	2
08/10/2021	29/10/2021	21	15/05/2023	16/05/2023	1
13/10/2021	18/10/2021	5	16/05/2023	25/05/2023	9
16/10/2021	28/11/2021	43	16/05/2023	16/06/2023	31
16/10/2021	15/03/2022	150	25/05/2023	26/05/2023	1
19/10/2021	05/11/2021	17	26/05/2023	01/07/2023	36
25/10/2021	09/11/2021	15	02/06/2023	05/06/2023	3
26/10/2021	29/10/2021	3	05/06/2023	09/06/2023	4
27/10/2021	06/11/2021	10	10/06/2023	29/11/2023	172
31/10/2021	03/11/2021	3	12/06/2023	14/06/2023	2
04/11/2021	04/11/2021	0	27/06/2023	19/12/2023	175
04/11/2021	04/11/2021	0	30/06/2023	27/10/2023	119
05/11/2021	22/11/2021	17	01/07/2023	04/07/2023	3
09/11/2021	12/11/2021	3	04/07/2023	20/07/2023	16
16/11/2021	23/11/2021	7	07/07/2023	12/07/2023	5
18/11/2021	19/11/2021	1	08/07/2023	23/08/2023	46
22/11/2021	15/03/2022	113	10/07/2023	18/03/2024	252
23/11/2021	26/11/2021	3	12/07/2023	14/07/2023	2
25/11/2021	03/12/2021	8	13/07/2023	30/01/2024	201
29/11/2021	01/12/2021	2	16/07/2023	01/08/2023	16
07/12/2021	08/12/2021	1	21/07/2023	08/08/2023	18
08/12/2021	21/01/2022	44	25/07/2023	22/08/2023	28
16/12/2021	21/12/2021	5	26/07/2023	04/08/2023	9
23/12/2021	24/12/2021	1	28/07/2023	01/08/2023	4
23/12/2021	31/12/2021	8	02/08/2023	03/08/2023	1
29/12/2021	04/01/2022	6	03/08/2023	04/08/2023	1
03/01/2022	07/01/2022	4	05/08/2023	28/11/2023	115
05/01/2022	06/01/2022	1	06/08/2023	07/08/2023	1
07/01/2022	10/01/2022	3	10/08/2023	18/08/2023	8
10/01/2022	11/01/2022	1	14/08/2023	15/08/2023	1
10/01/2022	21/01/2022	11	21/08/2023	06/09/2023	16
13/01/2022	28/01/2022	15	21/08/2023	22/08/2023	1
20/01/2022	28/01/2022	8	24/08/2023	06/09/2023	13
21/01/2022	26/05/2022	125	24/08/2023	20/12/2023	118
25/01/2022	18/12/2023	692	25/08/2023	11/09/2023	17
28/01/2022	16/03/2022	47	27/08/2023	16/10/2023	50
28/01/2022	28/01/2022	0	06/09/2023	01/11/2023	56
08/02/2022	27/05/2022	108	13/09/2023	18/09/2023	5
09/02/2022	18/02/2022	9	16/09/2023	19/09/2023	3

23/02/2022	28/02/2022	5	16/09/2023	18/09/2023	2
25/02/2022	01/03/2022	4	20/09/2023	16/11/2023	57
28/02/2022	02/03/2022	2	21/09/2023	11/10/2023	20
11/03/2022	07/04/2022	27	22/09/2023	09/01/2024	109
24/03/2022	31/08/2022	160	27/09/2023	29/09/2023	2
28/03/2022	11/04/2022	14	29/09/2023	17/10/2023	18
28/03/2022	30/03/2022	2	30/09/2023	06/10/2023	6
30/03/2022	21/04/2022	22	03/10/2023	04/10/2023	1
30/03/2022	19/04/2022	20	05/10/2023	18/10/2023	13
05/04/2022	11/04/2022	6	15/10/2023	19/10/2023	4
08/04/2022	12/04/2022	4	17/10/2023	19/10/2023	2
11/04/2022	14/04/2022	3	18/10/2023	23/10/2023	5
15/04/2022	29/04/2022	14	20/10/2023	21/12/2023	62
17/04/2022	19/04/2022	2	20/10/2023	24/10/2023	4
19/04/2022	19/04/2022	0	21/10/2023	27/10/2023	6
21/04/2022	26/04/2022	5	07/11/2023	10/11/2023	3
22/04/2022	25/04/2022	3	07/11/2023	08/11/2023	1
22/04/2022	16/11/2022	208	14/11/2023	15/11/2023	1
25/04/2022	15/06/2022	51	15/11/2023	02/02/2024	79
28/04/2022	29/04/2022	1	22/11/2023	09/04/2024	139
16/05/2022	17/05/2022	1	23/11/2023	06/12/2023	13
21/05/2022	23/05/2022	2	30/11/2023	11/12/2023	11
23/05/2022	24/05/2022	1	07/12/2023	30/01/2024	54
26/05/2022	14/04/2023	323	18/12/2023	19/12/2023	1
31/05/2022	06/06/2022	6	19/12/2023	21/12/2023	2
01/06/2022	13/06/2022	12	22/12/2023	04/01/2024	13
02/06/2022	24/06/2022	22	27/12/2023	15/01/2024	19
08/06/2022	22/06/2022	14	28/12/2023	15/01/2024	18
17/06/2022	24/06/2022	7	03/01/2024	15/01/2024	12
17/06/2022	23/06/2022	6	05/01/2024	05/01/2024	0
21/06/2022	30/06/2022	9	06/01/2024	16/01/2024	10
22/06/2022	24/06/2022	2	16/01/2024	27/03/2024	71
24/06/2022	04/07/2022	10	17/01/2024	06/02/2024	20
01/07/2022	06/07/2022	5	24/01/2024	25/01/2024	1
08/07/2022	11/07/2022	3	30/01/2024	31/01/2024	1
11/07/2022	23/08/2022	43	31/01/2024	16/02/2024	16
03/08/2022	26/09/2022	54	02/02/2024	06/02/2024	4
04/08/2022	05/08/2022	1	02/02/2024	03/02/2024	1
05/08/2022	17/08/2022	12	02/02/2024	27/02/2024	25
11/08/2022	26/08/2022	15	06/02/2024	17/02/2024	11
18/08/2022	05/12/2022	109	14/02/2024	16/04/2024	62
12/09/2022	26/10/2022	44	20/02/2024	12/04/2024	52
12/09/2022	13/09/2022	1	23/02/2024	13/03/2024	19
13/09/2022	16/09/2022	3	26/02/2024	27/02/2024	1
21/09/2022	23/12/2022	93	27/02/2024	29/02/2024	2

25/09/2022	27/09/2022	2	28/02/2024	19/03/2024	20
------------	------------	---	------------	------------	----

Appendix 7 – Hospital admissions related to delirium

DateAdmission	WardAdmit	PatientGroup	ClinicalCode	Code Description
07/10/2021	MM	General Rehabilitation	F051	Delirium superimposed on dementia
12/05/2022	W1	Respiratory	F059	Delirium, unspecified
16/09/2022	W1	Respiratory	F059	Delirium, unspecified
23/12/2022	W1	Respiratory	F059	Delirium, unspecified
09/02/2022	W3	Elderly	F051	Delirium superimposed on dementia
22/02/2022	W3	Elderly	F104	Mental and behavioural disorders due to use of alcohol (Withdrawal state with delirium)
31/03/2022	W3	Elderly	F051	Delirium superimposed on dementia
16/05/2022	W3	Elderly	F059	Delirium, unspecified
31/05/2022	W3	Elderly	F059	Delirium, unspecified
20/04/2023	W3	Elderly	F051	Delirium superimposed on dementia
22/05/2023	W3	Elderly	F059	Delirium, unspecified
27/07/2023	W3	Elderly	F051	Delirium superimposed on dementia
22/05/2021	W9	Stroke	F059	Delirium, unspecified
05/08/2021	W9	Stroke	F059	Delirium, unspecified
10/01/2022	W9	Stroke	F059	Delirium, unspecified
08/02/2022	W9	Stroke	F051	Delirium superimposed on dementia
08/04/2023	W9	Stroke	F051	Delirium superimposed on dementia

TRITECH

Sefydliad | Institute

TriTech Institute
Unit 2 Dura Park
Bynea
SA14 9TD

0300-303-6115

Tritech.HDD@wales.nhs.uk

 TriTech Institute

 @tritech_hd

 tritech.nhs.wales